

Pilot Program: Las Palmeras

Case Study

The Pilot **Training Program Las Palmeras** was a collaborative initiative between Bridge for Billions and the University of Córdoba (UCO), in a co-management effort within the scope of activities of IN-HABIT, H2020 European Union to empower women entrepreneurs in the Las Palmeras neighborhood, in Córdoba. This case study examines the **challenges, methodology, results, and areas for improvement of the program, demonstrating its potential for replication**. By adapting our traditional incubation program method to address the unique needs of underserved communities, Bridge for Billions can expand its impact and empower more early-stage entrepreneurs worldwide. Moving forward, Bridge for Billions remains committed to leveraging innovative approaches to democratize access to entrepreneurship and drive positive social change.

Challenges:

Las Palmeras (a disadvantaged neighborhood in Córdoba, Spain) presented significant barriers to successfully deploying the Bridge for Billions standard online training entrepreneurship incubation process. These bottlenecks included: very limited digital literacy, lack of access to the necessary technology (e.g.: laptops or tablets), and unfamiliarity with online learning environments or preparation to go through a comprehensive business development plan in only a few months. These challenges hindered the residents' ability to engage in our traditional entrepreneurship programs and be effectively fully onboarded in the incubation standard methodology.

Methodology:

To address these challenges, the pilot program involved the adaptation of a four-month course into an **eight-week hybrid format** tailored to the specific needs and skills of the participants.

Comprehensive support and collaboration between B4B and UCO were integral to the success of the program. The methodology included:

1. Conducting **needs assessments** to understand the unique challenges faced by participants.
2. **Roles within the program:** B4B developed the methodology and content presentation for all sessions, which were delivered online. UCO consistently arrived early every Monday before the online meetings to address questions, set up the session, connect the computer, and display the presentation. They also printed out homework and materials for the entrepreneurs to use during the session, and stayed afterward to assist with questions, homework, and other needs. This personalized support helped overcome the digital divide and ensured that participants could fully engage in the program despite limited access to technology or digital literacy.
3. **Profile of participants**
 - “Come bien, paga poco”- 5 women entrepreneurs: Toñi Carrillo, Carmen Montes, Soledad Pedregosa, Rafi Moreno, and Conchi Rabadán
 - They aim to provide traditional and vegan takeaway food to cater to dependent individuals, particularly, making their lives easier. Their concept includes offering catering services for schools, residences, events, and also serving daily meals to workers who eat outside of their homes and seek affordability and quality.
 - “Caprichos para el paladar”- 2 women entrepreneurs: Ana Soto and Carmen Aguilera
 - Their business idea is artisanal pastry based on homemade cakes and desserts like muffins, brownies, and cakes... A business that operates by order and always customizes orders for events or individuals. Additionally, we offer a range of vegan products to cater to a larger audience.
 - “Floristería Huele Bien”- 1 women entrepreneur Luisa Muñoz
 - Her flower shop, named 'Huele bien,' will be located in her neighborhood among familiar faces—those who know her and whom she knows well. The unique value of her shop lies in her personal touch as the heart and soul of the business. Many people in the community know her and appreciate her special qualities, which she believes will contribute to the success of her business in this location.
 - “Las Cositas de Maria José” - 1 women entrepreneur María José Sánchez

- Her business is sewing and crafts, such as decorated boxes, bottles, nutcrackers... all made from recycled materials to ensure sustainable products. She can also create personalized Christmas ornaments and anything related to decoration. The value of her products lies in their custom, unique, and artisanal nature, as they are made to order.
4. Designing and delivering **tailored 8 different training** sessions focusing on essential entrepreneurship topics.
- Introduction to the entrepreneurship program: In the first session, the entrepreneurs received their initial entrepreneurship course session to develop business ideas. Each group presented their business concepts and learned about the course structure.
 - Value Proposition: They refined ideas in four different businesses: cooking, baking, crafts, and floristry. They discussed their unique value proposition and target audience, considering how their offerings stand out and appeal to potential customers.
 - Competitors Map: They mapped out competitors. They discussed the unique value of their products relative to competition, viewing competition as a catalyst for growth rather than a threat.
 - Stakeholders Map: They were then divided into thematic groups to work on their ideas and share opinions. They filled out a worksheet with questions about competitor information regarding prices, quality, preferences for additional collaborations, and knowledge of necessary permits and where to obtain them.
 - Business and Marketing Plan: We discussed marketing and advertising strategies used by companies to attract customers based on their needs and emotions. We then focused on each group's marketing strategy for their product, defining their target audience and approach, and exploring cost-effective marketing strategies and potential gains.
 - Price and Costs: We studied pricing and cost analysis of competitor products or services to inform our business strategies. We analyzed real examples relevant to each neighbor's business, assessing potential benefits and costs. For the next session, our homework was to research competitor prices, calculate project costs, and choose a product for launch with an initial price.
 - Launch our products in the market: We focused on launching products to the market, explaining examples and resources for effective launches. We clarified questions from last week's task and worked in business groups on this week's assignment to refine our projects. We also discussed plans for our "closing session" where they introduced their products to the neighborhood using a budget of up to 40 euros for activities like tastings, signage, and decorations.

- Pitching skills: In our final session, we discussed guidelines for preparing speeches and proposals for our closing event. We enjoyed a presentation from a current entrepreneur that is incubating on our platform within the IN-HABIT program in Cordoba, Cristina Rentería. We also organized the next session, finalizing preparations for the presentations and designing promotional materials. As homework, the neighbors prepared a brief speech about their business, including what product they will showcase, why their business is unique, and their budget for presentation materials.
5. **Interactive Learning:** Recognizing the importance of flexibility in accommodating the diverse needs and preferences of participants, the program adopted a hybrid session delivery model. Each session was designed to be interactive and engaging, incorporating a combination of presentations, discussions, and hands-on activities. Participants were encouraged to actively participate, share insights, and collaborate with others, fostering a sense of community and mutual support.
 6. **Structured Assignments:** Following each session, participants were given "homework" assignments and research tasks to complete before the next session. These assignments were designed to reinforce learning, encourage critical thinking, and provide opportunities for participants to apply new concepts and skills to their entrepreneurial projects.
 7. **Progressive Learning:** The program followed a progressive learning trajectory, with each session building upon the knowledge and skills acquired in previous sessions. This incremental approach allowed participants to gradually develop their entrepreneurial ideas, refine their strategies, and overcome challenges encountered along the way.
 8. **Encouragement product grants:** Each participant was allocated a budget of up to 40 euros to invest in building a stand showcasing their entrepreneurial projects to the public. This hands-on activity not only provided practical experience in budget management but also fostered creativity and resourcefulness in designing and executing their stands. Additionally, participants gained valuable insights into marketing strategies, presentation skills, and customer engagement as they prepared to showcase their ventures in front of an audience.
 9. **EVENT:** The final event on April 8th at "El Merendero" marked a significant milestone for the women entrepreneurs, representing the official launch of their products and businesses. This was their inaugural public event where they had the opportunity to showcase their offerings, practice pitching skills, engage in public speaking, network with industry professionals and potential customers, and gain experience in selling their products.

This event was instrumental in providing a platform for these entrepreneurs to step into the spotlight, gain exposure, and receive valuable feedback from a diverse audience including government officials, experienced mentors, business leaders, and community members. It was not only a showcase of their creations but also a learning experience where they honed crucial entrepreneurial skills and built confidence in presenting their ventures to the public.

The event began with a speech by Marta Baenz from the University of Córdoba, followed by remarks from Paola Rosenberg, Program Manager of Bridge for Billions. Then, Rafael Domenech, a successful entrepreneur from Las Palmeras gave a speech about his business as an inspiring story, particularly aimed at empowering women entrepreneurs. His words served to motivate and encourage the participants, highlighting the potential for success and resilience in entrepreneurship. Each of the entrepreneurs then delivered their pitch, and the audience asked questions and provided feedback to help improve their businesses. Several entrepreneurs had gifts for the audience, as well as product samples for tasting.

At the conclusion of the event, certificates were presented to each participant to acknowledge the successful completion of the program, and official photos were taken. Following this, all participants stayed for networking, sharing insights about the projects, and more. It was a valuable opportunity for collaboration and exchange among entrepreneurs and the community.

Results:

Despite the challenges faced, the innovative methodology implemented in the IN-HABIT program yielded promising outcomes:

10. The combination of online and in-person sessions facilitated meaningful connections and collaboration among participants, fostering a supportive and inclusive learning community.
 - Here are the **key learnings** shared by the entrepreneurs:
 - Learning the fundamentals of starting and developing a business, understanding the importance of setting achievable goals for the chosen business idea.
 - Viewing competitors as a positive reference rather than just rivals, recognizing opportunities to learn and improve from their approaches.
 - Gaining valuable knowledge about the unique value proposition of their business, identifying what makes their ventures distinctive and meeting customer expectations effectively.
 - Understanding the concept of direct and indirect costs in business operations, providing essential insights even for those with prior business experience.
 - During the program, we asked entrepreneurs to rate their motivation level to continue entrepreneurship on a scale from 1 to 10. The average rating among all participants was **9.5**, demonstrating their high level of confidence and enthusiasm for pursuing their entrepreneurial projects after completing the training sessions.
11. **Eleven women entrepreneurs successfully completed the program** with tangible progress made on their entrepreneurial projects, culminating in the development of **four**

impactful & social ventures presented publicly during the program's closing event. This progress was evident in the creation of tangible outcomes such as refined product prototypes, business plans, marketing materials, and sales strategies. These achievements not only demonstrated their dedication and growth but also laid a solid foundation for their ventures to thrive. .

12. Successful co-management efforts between Bridge for Billions and UCO that could extend such opportunities for upcoming cohorts / programs.
13. The engagement of relevant local stakeholders attended the final event such as: Blanca Torrent Cruz, Deputy Mayor of the City Council of Córdoba; María Luisa Gómez, General Manager of IMDEEC (Municipal Institute for Economic Development and Employment of Córdoba); Rafael Domenech, a successful entrepreneur from Las Palmeras; a mentor from the regular cohort of INHABIT Córdoba; an entrepreneur from the INHABIT Córdoba cohort; María del Mar Delgado Serrano, project coordinator of INHABIT; partners and members of the University of Córdoba; a representative from Bridge for Billions; and neighbors from the Las Palmeras neighborhood. The networking session following the event was equally important as it facilitated meaningful connections, idea sharing, and collaboration among the entrepreneurs, mentors, partners, and community members. All of these stakeholders provided feedback, tips and future opportunities to the entrepreneurs.

Improvements:

14. Further refinement of the curriculum/sessions to address specific challenges faced by participants and maximize learning outcomes.
15. Strengthening partnerships and community engagement to foster long-term support for entrepreneurship initiatives in Las Palmeras.
16. Enhancing impact measurement methodologies presents a critical opportunity for improvement. Beyond traditional survey approaches, implementing a data-driven framework, including quantitative metrics and performance indicators, would provide deeper insights into program efficacy.

Resources:

17. Presentations of Methodology: [here](#)
18. Pictures of sessions: [here](#)
19. Pictures closing event: [here](#)
20. Survey at the middle of the program of Entrepreneurs: [here](#)
21. Radio interview closing session: [here](#)
22. Magazine of all Entrepreneurs: [here](#)

23. Blog by UCO about the event: [here](#)

24. Blogs of all sessions: [here](#)

25. Certificates for Entrepreneurs: [here](#)